

Shaping Ceramic Cores for Aerospace Application

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Abstract

Demand for higher turbine entry temperature for improved gas turbine efficiency has resulted in design of complex serpentine cooling channels in the castings. The investment casting (IC) process to produce these blades/vanes need cavities of these shapes made of ceramic material. The ceramic cores are of twisted aerofoil shape and have four sections as shown in Fig.1. Shaping ceramic to such complex shapes is possible only through Ceramic injection moulding (CIM). It is a hybrid process having design flexibility of plastic injection molding and diverse material choices from powder metallurgy. CIM process parameters, like holding pressure, melt & mould temperature, cooling time, ejection temperature etc, have associated shrinkage & warpage (S&W) which need to be controlled. Authors have proposed simulation based study to predict, quantify and minimize S&W deviations and defects like weld line, sink marks & air trap. Laser Coordinate measuring machine (CMM) was used to quantify the dimensional deviation in green and sintered ceramic cores as shown in fig.2. Optimisation studies for injection parameters had shown that different set of values are needed to minimise profile or length deviations in the ceramic core.

Keywords: Ceramic Core, Gas Turbine Blades, Shrinkage & warpage.

Fig. 1. A typical HPTB core showing different sections

Fig. 2. Dimensional Deviation result from Laser CMM

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